

File name: secure_FL_algorithm.pdf

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Type of file: pdf

Location: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15053825>

Size: 46 KB

Tool: Algorithm diagram (workflow) described in M. Wasilewska, H. Bogucka, „Protection Against Poisoning Attacks on Federated Learning-based Spectrum Sensing”, accepted for publication in *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 2025

File name: Simulation parameters_of_JSAC.pdf

Author: Małgorzata Wasilewska

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Location: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15053707>

Size: 185 KB

Tool: Table for simulation parameters for evaluating the algorithm described in M. Wasilewska, H. Bogucka, „Protection Against Poisoning Attacks on Federated Learning-based Spectrum Sensing”, accepted for publication in *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 2025

File name: Results_of_JSAC.pdf

Author: Małgorzata Wasilewska

Type of file: pdf

Location: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15053853>

Size: 1347 KB

Tool: Matlab generated simulation results for evaluating the algorithm described in M. Wasilewska, H. Bogucka, „Protection Against Poisoning Attacks on Federated Learning-based Spectrum Sensing”, accepted for publication in *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 2025
